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Impact Of Wodass For Self Sustenance On Rural Community Empowerment In Rural Community Of Nguru Local Government Area, Yobe State

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ABSTRACT

The aim and objectives of this research is to examine the impact WODASS for self-sustenance on rural community empowerment in Rural community of Nguru local government, Yobe state. this study adopted survey research design. method of data collected used in this study is questionnaire, where the primary method of data collection is used random sample, the sample size of this study is 120. Poor performance of government in meeting the socio-economic quests of citizens has been identified as one of the reasons behind the proliferation of community-based organizations (CBOs) in the new millennium. There are no policies put in place by government to empower women and youths and this pave way for nongovernmental organization to render assistance and empower women. The motivation behind this study is to examine the beneficiaries' perception on the activities of the WODASS toward empowering rural women in Nguru. The study is quantitative in nature and employed questionnaire as an instrument of data collection. The research finding revealed that WODASS contributed to the development of Nguru community. The study recommends that, there should be government intervention so as to foster rural development; and there is need for training and retraining of WODASS members.

Keywords: Community, Development, Rural, and WODASS

INTRODUCTION

Poor performance of government in meeting the socio-economic quests of citizens has been identified as one of the reasons behind the proliferation of community based organizations (CBOs) in the new millennium. Humphrey and Anthony, (2017) asserted that people in developing nations have until recently looked up to their governments to meet their basic socio-economic demands. The overwhelming need to accord rural development a priority so as to enable them contribute meaningfully to the socio-cultural and socio-economic development of Nigeria, bulk of Nigeria's wealth is derived from agriculture and oil which lies in abundant quantity in rural communities. Currently, over 80 % of the entire population lives in the rural area, but much has not been done in terms of social amenities and infrastructural facilities. The

neglect of the rural areas has not only resulted to the mass exodus of rural dwellers to the urban centers, but has also made the rural areas less attractive for socio-economic investment (Onyeozu, 2010).

The impact of Non-governmental organization on rural development in Nigeria community especially Ngarbi ward of Nguru local government area implies the provision of basic amenities such as good roads, electricity, pipe borne water, health care facilities, schools, human capacity building centers and other necessities of life pertaining to man's general wellbeing. The women development association of self-sustenance of the Ngarbi ward will be the major case study for assessing the impact. Ugwu (2013) reported that an environmental conservation association provided in service training programme for administrators and managers in public and private sectors and in Kenya, the Mazingira Institute (NGOs) spear headed tree planting campaign through sensitization of pupils in public schools. Specifically, NGOs in Nigeria contribute to national development in the areas of democracy and good governance, poverty alleviation, women empowerment, primary healthcare and other health related matters, education and functional literacy. The development of the girl child, environment, conflict resolution, drug abuse and human rights (Adeboyeji, 2006). Despite government and NGOs efforts, the human development index in the Nigeria especially in rural areas is far below countries like Kenya, Ghana and South Africa (UNDP, 2008). This may be because over 15 percent of total overseas development aid channel through NGOs are notoriously implemented.

Statement of the Problem

One of the challenges facing the Nigerian state since independence is how to improve the living standard of the rural dwellers. Even though about 70% of the country's population lives in the rural areas, the rural areas are yet to witness significant level of development. This is evident in the apparent lack of basic infrastructural facilities especially in the construction and maintenance of rural roads (Agboola, Ifesanya & Akanmu 2012).

Hartman (2017) stated that an estimated 2 million people go hungry every day in Bauchi; 1.5 million never had chance to go to school; 3 out of every 5 people who work full time do not earn enough to keep their family above the poverty level. Almost 4 out of every 5 children live in poverty and only 2 out of 5 children go to school. Also, the state has about 83.6% of its inhabitants living in poverty presently (Isah, 2019). Based on the NBS report of 2016, the primary school enrolment as at 2016 was 61.5%. This was poor compared to 82.3% recorded for South-South geo-political zone of Nigeria and 72.8% for neighbouring North Central geo-political zone of Nigeria.

Despite all the commitments by Government rural area are still characterized by a decline in terms of human development, such as high level of illiteracy, high rate school dropout, low enrolment, poor health, malnutrition, disease, high infant mortality rate, low level of life expectancy, poverty, unemployment, inadequate shelter and so on. The problem of poverty in the midst of plenty is primarily caused by the skewed nature of inadequate and poor income distribution in Nigeria. Neglect of rural infrastructure only helps to compound the problem of poverty in Nigeria. Rural-Urban migration which has seen to the loss of vibrant rural youths to cities would not have been as acute if priority had been given to rural infrastructure. The research work will basically identify the significant contribution of non-governmental, non-profitable organization in curtailing the problems facing rural areas in Ngarbi. Nguru LGA of Yobe State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study will be guided by the following research questions:

1. How the WODASS activities Does brought about self-sustainability among the rural women in Nguru L.G?
2. What are the beneficiaries' perceptions on the activities of WODASS toward empowering women in Nguru L.G?
3. What are the challenges of WODASS in discharging empowering program to rural women in Nguru LG?

Objectives of the Study

1. To explore how WODASS activities brought about self-sustainability among the rural women in Nguru L.G.

2. To examine the beneficiaries' perception on the activities of WODASS toward empowering women in Nguru L.G.
3. To examine challenges of WODASS in discharging empowering program to rural women in Nguru LG.

Hypotheses

H₀: There is no significant relationship between WODASS activities and improvement standard of living of the rural women in Nguru LG.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between WODASS activities and improvement standard of living of the rural women in Nguru LG.

Literature review and theoretical framework

Concept of Non-governmental Organizations (NGOs)

NGO is an umbrella term which encompasses a broad array of organizations, varying enormously according to their purpose, philosophy, sectoral expertise and scope of activities. In the development field, NGOs range from the large international organizations and charities (mostly based in developed countries) to small community based self-help groups in developing countries. Literature on NGOs makes a distinction between operational NGOs which are engaged primarily in designing and implementing projects, and advocacy NGOs whose main purpose is to defend or promote a specific cause (World Bank, 1996). NGOs have also been classified according to whether they are more relief or development-oriented; whether they are religious or secular; whether they stress service delivery or participation, and whether they are more public or private-oriented (Zacharia and George, 2008). According to Wagona's (2007) NGOs are non-membership support organizations involved in relief, rehabilitation or community development work in developed and especially developing or Third World countries. They are part of the civil arena which provides a third approach to development in addition, but not exclusive alternative to the market and the state.

The World Bank (2012) defines NGOs as many groups and institutions that are entirely or largely independent of government and that have primarily humanitarian or cooperative rather than commercial objectives. Benjamin (2016) defines NGOs as private, non-profit, professional organizations, with a distinctive legal character, concerned with public welfare goals (36). Willetts (2021) says that no generally accepted definition of NGOs exists, but there are three other generally accepted characteristics that exclude some organizations from being considered as NGOs. First, NGOs should not be political parties or governmental agencies. They should not be any institutions directly affiliated with any organizations of a government. In addition, they should not aim to achieve any political power through their activities. Second, they should not generate profit. Profit making companies are not NGOs. Third, all criminal groups should be excluded from the definition of NGOs, although they do not belong to governments or private companies.

Types of NGOs

A critical look at the workings of NGOs suggests that they vary considerably in structure. Lewis and Kanji (2009) reported that NGOs are generally difficult to categorise into straight forward groups because they exist between states and markets, and take many diverse organisational forms. Willetts (2002) has suggested that the most effective way to distinguish between NGOs is to obtain precise data on a range of different variables: the number of full-time employees, the number of members and the funding of the annual budget give measures of the size of any NGO; opinion poll data on recognition of and support for an NGO or its goals, along with the frequency of positive mentions in the news media give measures of its political strength; and rather subjective variables, such as the professional skill, knowledge and experience of the personnel matter for both operational and campaigning purposes (ACPDT, 2010).

Mostashari (2015) put NGOs under two groups: Operational and advocacy NGOs. He interpreted the difference between them as the choice between small-scale change achieved directly through projects and large-scale change promoted indirectly through influence on the political system. Willetts (2002) identified that operational NGOs seek to "achieve small-scale change directly through projects", while

advocacy NGOs seek to “achieve large-scale change promoted indirectly through influence of the political system.”

The defining activity of operational NGOs as Willetts (2002) noted is implementing projects while advocacy NGOs are concerned with holding demonstrations or campaigns to defend or promote a specific cause. Thus, operational NGOs need to possess an efficient headquarters bureaucracy, in addition to the operational staff in the field while advocacy NGOs is not really characterized by such administrative burdens. Operational NGOs focus on delivery of services and welfare. Advocacy NGOs focus on knowledge, awareness and acceptance creation through lobbying and activism, hence, can also be termed as campaigning NGOs.

Claudia (2003) grouped NGOs into two broad categories: according to their orientation and level of operation. NGO orientation refers to the type of activities they undertake (for instance, human rights, environmental, or development work). An NGO’s level of operation on the other hand indicates the scale at which it works, such as local, regional, national or international (CDU, 2006).

Based on orientation, Claudia (2003) found four types of NGOs: charitable, service, participatory and empowering NGOs. Charitable NGOs’ activities are directed towards meeting the needs of the poor such as distribution of food, clothing or medicine; provision of housing, transport, and schools. Service orientation NGOs engage in activities such as the provision of health, family planning or education services in which the programme is designed by the NGO and people are expected to participate in its implementation and in receiving the service. Claudia (2003) further noted that participatory NGOs are characterised by self-help projects where local people are involved particularly in the implementation of a project by contributing cash, tools, land, materials and labour. Empowering NGOs on the other hand aim at helping poor people develop a clearer understanding of the social, political and economic factors affecting their lives, and to strengthen their awareness of their own potential power to control their lives. In terms of differentiating NGOs according to level of operation, Claudia (2003) identified community based, city-wide, national and international NGOs. These categories are clearer in identifying the coverage of the NGOs’ operations.

Concept of Development

The concept of development cannot be strictly minimized to only one or two variables and its characteristics are apparently dynamic. However, it is not altogether a semantic escapism for us to search for a precise definition of the concept and how to separate it from related concepts.

Development is used to refer to the total transformation of a system thus when used to describe a nation, it describe the transformation of the various aspect of life of the nation. In fact, development implies a progression from a lower and often undesirable state to a high and preferred one. An aspect of a life of a nation that is always considered crucial has to do with the human aspect of development.

Development is also seen in terms of attacking wide spread of absolute poverty, reducing inequality, and unemployment. All these are being achieved within the context of a growing economy. This led to the redefinition of development with growth and meeting the basic needs of the masses of the population. Seers perhaps posed the fundamental questions relating to the meaning of development when he asserts that:—the question to ask about country’s development are therefore; what has been happening to poverty?, what has been happening to unemployment?, and what has been happening to inequality?; if all these three declined from high levels then beyond reasonable doubt this has been a period of development for the country concerned. If one or two of these problems have been growing worse, especially if all three have, it would be strange to call the result development even if per capital doubled, Benjamin (2016).

According to Todaro (2013) development is seen as a multidimensional process involving the re organization and reorientation of the entire economic and social system. This involves in addition to improvement of income and output, radical changes in institutional, social and administrative structures as well as popular attitudes customs and beliefs.

According to Rodney (2012) Development is a many sided process, at the individual level it implies change increased skills, capacity, greater freedom, creativity, self discipline, responsibility, and wellbeing. At the social group development implies and increasing capacity both internal and external relationship.

The Concept and Nature of Human Development

Human development is perceived by FRN (2010) as all activities and interventions as well as processes that are aimed at expanding people's choices and enhancing their capabilities. It is the total wellbeing of a country's citizens in terms of life expectancy, knowledge and standard of living. It is also concerned with the extent to which human capital drives the development process and acts as wealth creator.

However, the first UNDP report of 1990 conceptualized Human development as the process of enlarging people's choices. The most critical ones are to lead a long and healthy life, to be educated and to enjoy a decent standard of living. Additional choices include political freedom, guaranteed human rights and self-respect. In this regard, Human Development denotes both the process of widening people's choices and the level of their achieved well-being. It also helps to distinguish clearly between two sides of human development. One is the formation of human capabilities, such as improved health or knowledge. The other is the use that people make of their acquired capabilities, for work or leisure.

Human development can be simply defined as a process of enlarging choices. Everyday human beings make a series of choices – some economic, some social, some political, some cultural. If people are the proper focus of development efforts, then these efforts should be geared to enhancing the range of choices in all areas of human Endeavour for every human being. Human development is both a process and an outcome. It is concerned with the process through which choices are enlarged, but it also focuses on the outcomes of enhanced choices.

Human development thus defined represents a simple notion, but one with far reaching implications. First, human choices are enlarged when people acquire more capabilities and enjoy more opportunities to use those capabilities. Human development seeks not only to increase both capabilities and opportunities but also to ensure an appropriate balance between them in order to avoid the frustration that a mismatch between the two can create. Second, as already implied, economic growth needs to be seen as a means, albeit an important one, and not the ultimate goal, of development. Income makes an important contribution to human well-being, broadly conceived, if its benefits are translated into more fulfilled human lives, but the growth of income is not an end in itself. Third, the human development concept, by concentrating on choices, implies that people must influence the processes that shape their lives. They must participate in various decision-making processes, the implementation of those decisions, and their monitoring and adjustment to improve outcomes where necessary.

In the ultimate analysis, human development is development of the people, development for the people, and development by the people. Development of the people involves building human capabilities through the development of human resources. Development for the people implies that the benefits of growth must be translated into the lives of people, and development by the people emphasizes that people must be able to participate actively in influencing the processes that shape their lives.

Concept of Rural Development

The term is used to Benjamin (2016) mean 'organizing things' so as to change existing conditions in favour of a better state. There may be many variants of development drawing their nomenclature from the sphere of activity where the change is managed or the type of change or the 'method' how the desired change is attained.

The concept of rural development in Nigeria lacks a unified definition as different scholars tend to view it from varying perspective. Some scholars look at rural development from the aspect of education/training (Denhardt *et al.*, 2009). UNDP (2009) perceived rural development to involve creating and widening opportunities for (rural) individuals to realize full potential through education and share in decision and action which affect their lives. He also viewed the efforts to increase rural output and create employment opportunities and root out fundamental (or extreme) cases of poverty, diseases and ignorance. Others like Freire and Smith (2007) viewed rural development as means for the provision of basic amenities, infrastructure, improved agriculture productivity and extension services and employment generation for rural dwellers. An understanding of the concept of development will give a clearer picture of rural development.

Hornby (2001) defined development as the gradual growth of something so that it becomes more advanced, stronger, etc; the process of producing or creating something new. The definition implied that

development involves a gradual or advancement through progressive changes. Umebali (2006) sees the changes to be multi-dimensional involving changes in structures, attitude and institutions as well as the acceleration of economic growth, reduction of inequality and eradication of absolute poverty. He concluded that development involves economic growth component, equality or social justice component, and socio-economic transformational component which are all on a self-sustaining basis.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework adopted for this study is the Participatory Development Approach. The details of this theory are discussed below:

Participatory Approaches in theory have developed over the years from extractive one-sided appraisals (Rapid Rural Appraisals (RRA)) to mutual two sided approaches such as Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA). PRA describes a family of approaches and methods to enable rural people to share, enhance, and analyse their knowledge of life and conditions, to plan and to act, to monitor and evaluate.

METHODOLOGY

The population for the study was made up of the entire people in the community and the staffs of WODASS association. One hundred and twenty (120) respondents were randomly sampled from the population. The study will adopt a cross sectional sample survey. Primary data was used for data collection in this study. These data will be obtained through the use of structured questionnaire and oral interview. Descriptive statistics will to analysis the data and Correlation and regression analysis was used to test the hypothesis.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Analysis of Collected Data

Table 1: The WODASS association provides aids in terms of cash.

Items	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	57	59.4%
Disagree	20	18%
Undecided	43	22.6%
Total	120	100%

Source: Field survey 2026.

Table 1 above shows that 57 accounting for 59.4% of the respondents agree that the association provides aids in terms of cash, 20 representing 18% disagree, and 43 representing 22.6% are with no choice. This results shows that WODASS association provides aids in terms of cash.

Table 2: People in the community are very pleased with the activities of WODASS in empowering youths.

Items	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	76	46.4%
Disagree	16	16.5%
Undecided	28	37.1%
Total	120	100%

Source: Field survey 2026.

Table 2 above shows that 76 representing 46.4% of the respondents agree that people of Durr community are very pleased with the activities of WODASS in empowering youths, while 16 representing 16.5% of the respondent disagree and 28 representing 37.1% of the respondent are with no choice. This result shows that beneficiaries are very pleased with the activities of WODASS in empowering youths.

Table 3: The activities of the association impacts the community positively

Items	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	76	45.7%
Disagree	32	29.1%
Undecided	12	25.2%
Total	120	100%

Source: Field survey 2026.

Table 3 above shows that 76 accounting for 45.7% of the respondents agree that the activities of the association impacts the community positively, 32 representing 29.1% disagree, and 12 representing 25.2% are with no choice. This result shows that the activities of the association impact the community positively.

Table 4: The people in the community are happy to have WODASS in our community because they provide relief materials

Items	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	72	55.8%
Disagree	32	35.6%
Undecided	16	8.6%
Total	120	100%

Source: Field survey 2026.

Table 4 above shows that 72 representing 55.8% of the respondents' agree that people of the community are happy to have WODASS in their community because they provide relief materials, while 32 representing 35.6% of the respondents disagree and 16 representing 8.6% of the respondents are with no choice. This result shows that people of the community are happy to have WODASS in their community because they provide relief materials.

Table 5: WODASS activities do not engage other stakeholders in their operation.

Items	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	37	37.1%
Disagree	14	20.5%
Undecided	69	42.4%
Total	120	100%

Source: Field survey 2026.

Table 5 above shows that 37 accounting for 37.1% of the respondent agree that WODASS activities do not engage other stakeholders in their operation, 14 representing 20.5% of the respondent disagree and 69 representing 42.4% of the respondent have no choice. This result shows more undecided respondents are the majority.

Hypothesis testing

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.690 ^a	.476	.463	2.806
a. Predictors: (Constant), TBP, TWA, TC				
b. Dependent Variable: TSD				

Where R^2 = is the percentage of the response variable variation that is explained by a linear model. Or:
 $R\text{-squared} = \text{Explained variation} / \text{Total variation}$

Table

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	9.107	1.036		8.788	.000
	TBP	.155	.146	.163	1.058	.000
	TWA	.490	.101	.660	4.842	.000
	TC	.187	.114	.206	1.642	.000
a. Dependent Variable: TSD						

The hypotheses of the study shows that the relationship between Beneficiaries Perception and Sustainability is significant, strong and positive (.163, $P>0.05$), This outcome is interpreted to mean that 84% increase in Beneficiaries will elicit 100% increase in sustainability development in rural area of Nguru positively is at 5% level of significance. WODASS activities and sustainability development is strong and positive (.660, $p>0.05$). This outcome is interpreted to mean that 34% increase in increase in WODASS will elicit 100% increase in sustaining development in Nguru at 5% level of significance. Likewise the relationship between challenges facing rural area of Nguru and Sustainable development is strong and positive (.206, $P>0.05$). This outcome is interpreted to mean that 80% increase in addressing challenges facing WODASS will elicit 100% increase in sustaining development in Nguru at 5% level of significance.

DISCUSSION OF THE MAJOR FINDINGS

To answer this question, responses to table 1,2,3,4, and 5 were analyzed, in which the study found that: The association provides aids in terms of cash; people in the community are very pleased with the activities of WODASS, WODASS empower youths, the activities of the association impacts the community positively and people in the community are happy to have WODASS in their community because they provide relief materials;and WODASS activities do not engage other stakeholders in their operationThe above findings were corroborated by vast literatures to support these findings among which is the study of Christiana, (2019) on the impact of women development on rural community empowerment in Nguru local government prostrates that women association has worked to support the empowerment of women, youth and children from its inception. The association focus is in the areas of Health, Education, Micro credit meaning promoting women resilience in business and agriculture through the village savings and loan scheme in Nguru LGA, Water and Sanitation, civic education, governance and human right, peace education and peace building, anti-corruption and vocational skills acquisition programme for economic empowerment and self reliance at Waziri Madu Adolescent Girls Center, Ngarbi Nguru LGA in Bauchi State.

CONCLUSION

Conclusively, it can be concluded that NGOs contributed to development at rural and other levels of government. This can be seen in this study the association provides aids in terms of cash; people in the community are very pleased with the activities of WODASS, WODASS empower youths, they provide relief materials.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made;

1. State and local governments should encourage small and medium NGOs to prosper development in rural areas.
2. Membership of WODASS should be expended to captured critical stakeholders. This will expose their operation to certain level.
3. The association should improve it source of fund to cater for more women and youths in the area as there is high need for that.
4. The association should collaborate with other NGOs to include sectors such as agriculture and others.
5. There is need for the association train and retrain their members to boost their performance and reduce level of technical challenges .

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